

Supplement to the manuscript " Implementation of an electronic, secure web-based application to support routine hand hygiene observation with immediate direct feedback and anonymised benchmarking "

'CleanHands' Development

Technical Description

Application Concept

Architecture

The demand for an environment that is as platform-independent as possible for mobile devices can be optimally fulfilled by a web application. This reduces the requirements for the various platforms to the availability of a web browser and an - at least temporarily available - internet connection. PHP [1] is one of the most widely used programming language for creating web applications and therefore presents itself as the appropriate technology in conjunction with the database management system MYSQL [2]. The Model-View-Controller pattern is used as an architectural pattern for structuring the application. Attention is paid to a separation between the data models, the presentation of the data and the application control.

Components

To ensure easy expandability, the system consists of a number of individual independent components. The components are functional subunits of varying complexity that communicate with each other via defined interfaces. A hierarchical overview of the main components of the system can be found in Table 1. Some special features of the components are explained below.

CleanHands		
Application core	Modules	User interfaces
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Database connection• Session management• Cryptography• Data backup• Localisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Hand hygiene module• Institutions• Attributes• User• User groups• Graphics library• Import / Export	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Mobile data acquisition• Analysis• Administration

Table 1: Main components of CleanHands

Application core

Database connection

In addition to providing the interfaces to the database system, all transactions to the database are logged by the component. This means that changes to the databases can be traced back exactly (audit trail).

Session management

It is responsible for the unique identification of the user and includes the login and logout process and the management of the user's application settings. The user is authenticated by combining his or her personal password with a salt. A salt is a randomly chosen string of characters used in cryptography to increase the entropy of the input (and thus the security of the password).

Cryptography

To ensure data protection, critical information is stored in encrypted form. It should not be possible to assign the observations in the database to a ward or an observer without appropriate access rights. To encrypt the association between observations and wards or observers, a random number is generated for each ward and for each observer. These random numbers are encrypted and stored in the tables for wards or observers as ciphertext. The cipher algorithm used is the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) with a key length of 256bit.

Localisation

The application is designed so that the user interface supports several languages between which the user can choose. The translations can be done in the application itself.

Modules

The modules are primarily responsible for creating new entries of the corresponding type in the database, edit elements or delete them.

Institutions

The institutions are organised hierarchically, with a distinction made between hospital group, hospital and wards.

Attributes

Any number of attributes can be assigned to each institution. The individual attributes are grouped together. For example, an attribute group "unit" can be created to assign a ward to a specific unit e.g. medicine, surgery, geriatrics etc. This allows grouping wards into units. During the analysis, the hand hygiene adherence of the different units can then be compared with each other (benchmarking).

Users and user groups

With the help of user groups, access rights to CleanHands can be precisely defined. All actions can be enabled or disabled individually. If users are added to a user group, they automatically inherit the access rights. At the user level, it can be further defined which institutions they have access to.

Graphics library

The freely available JpGraph library [3] is used as a basis for generating the graphics for the analysis.

Import / Export

For the import and export of data, the widely used file format CSV (comma-separated values) is used.

Implementation

The basic structure of CleanHands is shown in Figure 1. The source code of the entire web application consists of about 65'000 lines of application code distributed over 200 files. As a user you interact with one of the three graphical user interfaces.

Mobile data acquisition

The data entry screens for smartphones and tablets are optimised for easy data entry. Large buttons with pictograms increase usability. The last observations can be verified by means of a fade-in history and corrected in case of incorrect entry. An offline functionality ensures that observations can be recorded despite the absence of an internet connection. These observations are stored fully encrypted in the local memory of the unit and can be transferred later when the connection is established. To use this functionality, one must have logged in at least once on the unit. No further installations are necessary.

Analysis

Analysis can be done either on the computer or on a mobile device. The user can freely select available parameters as filters or use them to subdivide the analysis. The data is presented in the form of bar charts. For each bar, the number of observations, the hand hygiene adherence values in percent and the 95% confidence intervals can be displayed. For the calculation of the 95% confidence interval, the Wilson score with continuity correction can optionally be used. This is particularly suitable for small samples and probability close to 0% or 100% better than the simple approximation by the normal distribution. The display can be adapted to one's own wishes through numerous settings. The data can be exported as a CSV file for further processing.

Administration

All administrative tasks are accessible via a menu. The individual menu items are displayed or hidden depending on the user's access rights. Routine procedures here include creating or activating new users, assigning access rights, maintaining lists of institutions and assigning attributes to institutions. Incorrect entries can be corrected retrospectively. In addition to the automatic data backup, backups can be created manually and downloaded or restored. An application log can also be viewed.

Figure 1: basic structure of CleanHands

References

- [1] PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor 2022. <https://www.php.net/> (accessed March 30, 2022).
- [2] MySQL 2022. <https://www.mysql.com/> (accessed March 30, 2022).
- [3] JpGraph - Most powerful PHP-driven charts 2022. <https://jpgraph.net/> (accessed March 30, 2022).